

Correlation of Biomarkers In the Clinical Study of Accelerated Orthodontics

Nanda Kishore¹
Pradeep Raghav²
Amit Kumar Khara³
Anusha Jaiswal⁴
Aakashdeep⁵

PG Student¹
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut

Professor and Head²
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut

Professor³
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut

PG Student⁴
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut

PG Student⁵
Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial
Orthopaedics
Subharti Dental College and Hospital
Meerut

Submitted 01 October 2025
Accepted 11 October 2025
Published xx xxx xxxx

Access this article online
Website : www.updent.in
DOI
Quick Response Code

Abstract

This article explores the correlation of biomarkers in clinical studies on accelerated orthodontics, focusing on techniques to reduce treatment time and improve patient comfort. Methods such as Low Level Laser Therapy (LLLT), vibrations, photobiomodulation, and electric current, along with surgical techniques like corticotomy, Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO), micro-osteoperforations, and piezoscision, are highlighted for their effectiveness in accelerating orthodontic tooth movement (OTM).

The review underscores the importance of biomarkers such as RANK, OPG, RANKL, interleukins, and matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) in monitoring bone and periodontal tissue remodeling. A literature search on PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar, and Web of Science identified 35 relevant articles. Findings show that surgical approaches increase the RANKL, IL-1 β , and OPG, enhancing OTM. Physical stimuli like photobiomodulation and electric currents promote collagen turnover, MMP expression, and interleukin levels, while pharmacological methods using cytokines and prostaglandins accelerate OTM through localized injections and gene transfer.

It is concluded that there is a marked increase in biomarker activity while accelerating the orthodontic tooth movement by various methods leading to the alveolar bone remodeling and modeling accompanied by bone formation on the tension side and bone resorption on the compressed side.

Introduction

Orthodontics aim is to achieve efficient and effective tooth movement, which has driven the development of materials and procedures that enhance patient comfort and shorten treatment time¹. Tooth movement is facilitated by applying directed forces that induce changes in the bone and periodontal ligament, releasing mediators in gingival crevicular fluid, saliva, and other body fluids². These forces trigger a cascade of cellular and molecular events, conditioning microenvironments to respond to bone bending and tissue remodeling³.

Osteoclastic activity affects tooth-supporting biomarkers such as RANK, RANKL, and osteoprotegerin (OPG), with OPG inhibiting RANKL-driven osteoclastogenesis. The matrix metalloproteinase (MMP) family also plays a vital role in the remodeling of bone⁴. To hasten the orthodontic tooth movement (OTM), minimally invasive methods like Low Level Laser Therapy (LLLT), vibrations,

photobiomodulation, and electric current are favored over invasive techniques like corticotomy. Additionally, pharmacological agents such as Prostaglandin-2, Vitamin D, and Relaxin are employed to enhance tooth movement⁵.

Method

Research publications were searched for 5 months on PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar and Web of Science, and the articles with the terms accelerated orthodontic, Osteoclastogenesis, Inflammatory markers, Orthodontic tooth movement, RANK, RANKL, OPG. The articles were further analyzed to investigate how biomarkers correlate in clinical studies when accelerating tooth movement using various methods of accelerated orthodontics.

How to Cite This Article : Kishore et al. -

Results

Finally, 35 articles were collected and they were used to formulate this review

Discussion

Biomarkers Of Orthodontic Tooth Movement

A biomarker is a substance that can be used to monitor and quantitatively assess pathogenic processes, normal physiological processes, or pharmacological responses to therapeutic interventions. An ideal biomarker should be sensitive, specific, and capable of providing information about the biological state, particularly regarding changes in periodontal tissue and their relation to specific stages of orthodontic tooth movement (OTM). Understanding the cellular processes involved helps determine the appropriate mechanical loading, thereby minimizing the treatment period and potentially avoiding side effects from orthodontic therapy⁶.

Accelerated Orthodontic

It refers to a technique that speeds up tooth movement without adverse effects, accomplished through surgical, physical, or pharmacological approaches.

Accelerating Tooth Movement By Surgical Approaches

Surgical interventions in orthodontics have become notable for their ability to accelerate tooth movement while maintaining treatment effectiveness and patient safety.

The various methods used are,

- Corticotomy
- PAOO
- Microosteoperforations (Mops)
- Piezocision

1. Corticotomies

Kawakami et al.⁷ performed a study on histological responses at the corticotomy site, observing increased remodeling of bone cells, widened sutures, and irregular cell and fiber arrangement. According to the study conducted by Wang et al.⁸, corticotomy induced acceleration of osteoporosis occurs at the cellular level by promoting infiltration of macrophage via the JAK/STAT3 and NF-κB pathways during the early and late phases.

2. Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO)

Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO) is a type of treatment method that integrates selective alveolar corticotomy, orthodontic force application, and particulate bone grafting. According to a study conducted by Jiaqi Wu et al.⁹ which explored protein changes in GCF at various moments after PAOO using proteomics methods to identify significant bone metabolism related biomarkers, the authors found a total of one thirty four proteins selected based on keywords such as osteoblast markers, osteoclastogenesis, regulating genes, osteoclast markers and inflammatory markers. Among these, 5 proteins identified through label free quantitative proteomics were KLF10, FBN1, APOA1, SYT7, and NOTCH1. The study noted a rapid increase in NOTCH1 levels within the first two weeks after PAOO, followed by a slower growth trend.

3. Micro-osteoperforation

Micro-osteoperforation is an efficient, comfortable, and safe procedure that accelerates the movement of tooth and reduces the duration of treatment significantly. Alikani et al.¹⁰ (Fig 1) found in their clinical study that osteoclast activity is crucial in regulating bone resorption, impacting the speed of tooth movement. Orthodontic forces usually trigger increased inflammatory markers, like chemokines and cytokines, which are vital for recruiting precursor cells for osteoclasts and aiding in their differentiation into mature osteoclasts. Their study concluded that micro-osteoperforations increased tooth movement rates by 2.3 times, accompanied by a notable rise in inflammatory marker levels.

A similar study conducted by Raghav P et al.¹¹ (Fig 2,) assessed the impact of micro-osteoperforations (MOPs) on canine retraction rates and biomarker expression in gingival crevicular fluid (GCF). The results of this study showed a significant difference in canine retraction rates only during the initial 4 weeks, with no significant difference observed from weeks 8 to 16 between the MOPs and control groups. Additionally, there was a notable increase in alkaline and acid phosphatase activity in GCF during the first 4 weeks of retraction of canine in the MOPs group in contrast to the control, indicating increased biomarker activity during the initial treatment period.

4. Piezocision

Piezocision, is a surgical procedure that is minimally invasive, and has been utilized to hasten tooth movement. Yildirim et al.¹² performed a study to assess GCF levels of osteocalcin (OC) and type I collagen cross-linked C-terminal telopeptide during canine distalization without and with piezocision. They found that GCF OC levels on the compression side and ICTP levels on the tension side were lower in the piezocision group.

Additionally, Fernandes T et al.¹³ evaluated the impact of piezocision (PZ) in hastening maxillary canine retraction and its impact on various remodeling of bone markers in GCF. Their analysis revealed higher IL-1β levels at the 2nd and 12th weeks, with no significant differences in TNF-α expression between the experimental and control groups. OPG levels were elevated on the experimental side at the 2nd and 12th weeks, while RANKL levels were more on the experimental side. Furthermore, DKK1 levels on the experimental side were reduced at the 4th week in this clinical study.

Accelerating Tooth Movement By Physical Stimuli

1. Direct Electric Currents and Pulsed Electromagnetic Fields

In 1987, Stark and Sinclair¹⁴ conducted a study examining the impact of pulsed electromagnetic fields on pigs, using the piezoelectric theory. Their findings revealed a nearly doubled rate of movement (tooth) ($0.42 \pm 0.17\text{mm}$) compared to the control group ($0.28 \pm 0.08\text{mm}$), indicating enhanced protein metabolism in the study group. They also noted notable elevation in the quantity of osteoclasts and elevated levels of creatinine uric acid, along with creatinine phosphokinase.

Similarly, Spadari et al.¹⁵ found that stimulation of electrical current (10 μ A/5 min) combined with force application improved tissue responses. This combination modulated the expression of TGF- β 1, bFGF, and VEGF while also affecting the quantity of granulocytes, blood vessels, fibroblasts, and osteoclasts. However, despite the positive correlation between stimulation of electrical current and accelerated OTM, further research involving human participants is recommended for a more conclusive outcome. This suggestion comes from a meta-analysis and systematic review by Dutta et al.¹⁶ on the application of stimulation of electrical current in accelerated orthodontics.

2. Vibratory Stimulus

Krishtab et al.¹⁷ pioneered the utilization of vibratory stimulation to accelerate tooth movement, marking a significant advancement in the field. Building on this foundation, Ohmae et al.¹⁸ further refined the technique by introducing ultrasonic vibration, which effectively enhanced the rate of tooth movement. Nishimura et al.¹⁹ invented a vibration incorporated system with a specific frequency (sixty one \pm 8.375Hz), applied to male Wistar rats' maxillary molars, owing to the notable increase in tooth movement rate. The group which is treated exhibited an increase in the presence of osteoclasts when compared with the control group, indicating the effectiveness of vibrational stimulation. The elevated RANKL expression in the resonance vibration group is disclosed by immunohistochemistry analysis, suggesting improved osteoclast survival, function, and generation.

Chatmahamongko et al.²⁰ compared the quantity of OPG, RANKL, IL-6, and IL-1 β in compressed human alveolar bone osteoblasts subjected to vibratory stimuli with a control that didn't receive vibration. They found nothing significant in expression between the experimental and control groups.

3. Photobiomodulation

To stimulate or inhibit biological activities with light energy at particular intensities, wavelengths, and irradiation regimens is known as photobiomodulation.

Low level laser therapy

Low level laser therapy (LLLT) is a focal point for its role in hastening tooth movement and supporting the remodeling of bone processes. Studies employing LLLT in animal models have consistently demonstrated notable improvements in tooth movement speed, often accompanied by positive changes in osteoblastic and osteoclastic activities within bone tissue. Notably, Kawasaki and Shimizu²¹ observed a significant 1.3 times increase in speed of tooth movement, along with heightened osteoclast and osteoblast activity during the remodeling of bone in a rat model.

However, research by Limpanichkul et al.²² involving 12 young adult patients found no substantial differences in tooth movement with a comparison of the experimental group and control group over a 111 month period. This outcome was attributed to the relatively low dosage of LLLT administered (25 J/cm²). Additionally, it was noted that irradiation with

laser stimulates osteoclastogenesis and enhances remodeling of bone by activating the pathway of M-CSF/c-fms, as concluded by Fujita et al.²³.

Various molecules are identified in the process of low level laser induced acceleration of tooth movement. These include increased turnover of collagen type- I and fibronectin (Kim et al.,²⁴), elevated expression of cathepsin K, MMP-9, and alpha (v) beta (3) integrins (Yamaguchi et al.,²⁵), and statistically significant rise in the quantity of OPG and RANKL in the GCF (Dominiquez et al.,²⁶). Moreover, higher levels of interleukins have been linked to increased remodeling of bone induced by orthodontic treatment forces in recent laser irradiation studies (Varella et al.,, Fernandes et al., 27).

Light emitting diode (LED) therapy

Research exploring the efficacy of light emitting diode (LED) therapy has primarily focused on its ability to expedite tooth movement and improve orthodontic outcomes. LED therapy functions by delivering specific light wavelengths to targeted areas, stimulating cellular activity, and encouraging tissue regeneration. This area of study has yielded promising findings, with several studies indicating faster tooth movement and reduced treatment durations when incorporating LED therapy into orthodontic protocols.

Studies in rats using LED mediated photobiomodulation therapy found reduced root resorption (Ekizer et al.,²⁸) and quicker resolution of crowding (Kau et al.,²⁹). Fernandes et al.²⁷ describe the velocity of intrusion of 0.26 mm/month in the irradiated group compared to 0.17 mm/month in the group that is not irradiated over an eight month period. Additionally, there was a significant increase in cytokine levels in the photobiomodulation group compared to the group of control, indicating a positive impact of LED therapy on cytokine activity.

Shankar et al.³⁰ conducted a study assessing GCF, prostaglandin-E2 (PGE-2) and interleukin 1-beta (IL1- β) levels, after the placement of elastic separators without or with low level laser therapy(). Their findings indicated that low level laser therapy reduced inflammatory markers like prostaglandin-E2 (PGE-2) and interleukin 1-beta (IL1- β) in patients using separators, suggesting an association between biomarkers and laser treatment.

Accelerating Tooth Movement Pharmacological Approaches

Local Cytokine Delivery

Cytokines, which are signaling proteins found extracellularly, play crucial roles in inflammation and remodeling of bone, both vital processes for osteogenesis malformation (OTM). Krishnan and Davisovitch² highlight that cytokines also support the development, activation, and death of periodontal ligament (PDL) cells. This assertion is reinforced by heightened cytokine levels during tooth movement, including TNF- α , interleukins, and RANKL. Moreover, interleukin activities are influenced by increased production of macrophage colony-stimulating factor and PGE2, which promote osteoclast

development.

Research by Saito et al.³¹ illustrated that cells can respond to multiple stimuli simultaneously. In experiments without the cytokine IL-1 β (as a control group), fibroblasts released minimal PGE2 into the incubation media. However, the existence of IL-1 β significantly increased prostaglandin E2 (PGE2) production in these cells³².

Prostaglandins (Pgs)

Prostaglandins (PGs), a type of lipid, are not stored within cells but are enzymatically produced in the cell membrane from fatty acids by cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes. Klein and Raisz demonstrated in 1970 that PGs induce osteoclastic hyperplasia, showcasing their bone resorbing capabilities.

In a study by Lee³³, after administering PGE1, a histological examination of paradental tissues revealed osteoclast appearance within six hours of force application, peaking within three days. Brudvik and Rygh discovered a potential downside in rats following local PGE2 injection, indicating a propensity for root resorption. Leiker et al. observed that a single PGE2 injection (at low doses of 0.1–1.0 μ g) significantly accelerated tooth movement, with repeated injections showing minimal impact.

Patil et al. performed a clinical study on 15 patients using a small dose of 1.0 μ g PGE1 combined with lignocaine to reduce pain. They found a notable increase (1.7:1) in distal canine retraction rate, consistent with Yamasaki et al.³⁴ Follow-up radiographs did not show root resorption evidence. Eltimamy et al. noted conflicting evidence on tooth movement acceleration with prostaglandins, while Spoerri et al. found no association of prostaglandin injections on root resorption.

RANKL

RANKL is a type of cytokine that regulates the function and formation, the cells responsible for bone resorption, and survival of osteoclasts. RANKL is essential for optimal bone metabolism.

The study conducted by Kanzaki et al.³⁵, Li et al. found that increased osteoclastic activity by locally injecting the RANKL.

Conclusion

Biomarkers are pivotal in accelerated orthodontics, impacting tooth movement rates and overall treatment success. Surgical, physical, and pharmacological methods showcase distinct interactions with biomarkers, influencing tooth movement rates and remodeling of bone.

- In surgical methods of accelerating tooth movement, the study of biomarker levels in the GCF shown that RANKL levels, IL-1 β levels, and OPG levels were higher on the experimental side whereas TNF- α expression didn't show significant differences and DKK1 levels were lower.
- In physical stimulus for accelerating the movement of the tooth, many other molecules have been identified such as increased turnover of collagen type I and fibronectin, increased cathepsin K, expression of MMP-9, and α V β 3 and even statistically significant increases in the release of

OPG and RANKL in the GCF.

- In photobiomodulation, greater levels of interleukins (IL-8, IL-6, and IL-1 β) have been associated with greater remodeling of bone brought on by orthodontic forces.
- Electrical stimulation enhanced tissue responses, modulating the expression of VEGF, TGF β 1, and bFGF while decreasing the quantity of granulocytes and increasing the quantity of fibroblasts, blood vessels, and osteoclasts.
- In the low level vibratory method, significant differences in the expression of RANKL, OPG, IL6, and IL-1 β were not seen.

In the pharmacological methods, either done by a local gene transfer or local injection, all the various methods aimed at release of agents that are injected over a time period, inducing reaction of inflammation or expression of protein respectively.

Overall, integrating biomarker analysis into clinical studies of accelerated orthodontics holds great promise for advancing treatment protocols, improving patient outcomes, and ultimately transforming the landscape of orthodontic care.

Reference

1. Kusy RP, Whitley JQ. Friction between different wire-bracket configurations and materials. *SeminOrthod.* 1997; 3 (3): 166-77.
2. Krishnan V, Davidovitch ZE. Cellular, molecular, and tissue-level reactions to orthodontic force. *Am J Orthod Dento-facial Orthop.* 2006;129 (4): 469-72.
3. Erdur EA, Karakasli K, Oncu E, Ozturk B, Hakkı S. Effect of injectable platelet-richfibrin (i-PRF) on the rate of tooth movement: A randomized clinical trial. *Angle Orthod.* 2021; 91 (3): 285-92
4. Kumar AA, Saravanan K, Kohila K, Kumar SS. Biomarkers in orthodontic tooth movement. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci.* 2015; 7 (2): 325-30.
5. Meikle MC. The tissue, cellular, and molecular regulation of orthodontic tooth movement: 100 years after Carl Sandstedt. *Eur J Orthod.* 2006; 28 (3): 221-40.
6. Taba M, Kinney J, Kim AS, Giannobile WV. Diagnostic biomarkers for oral and periodontal diseases. *Dental Clinics.* 2005; 49 (3): 551-71.
7. Kawakami T, Nishimoto M, Matsuda Y, Deguchi T, Eda S. Histological suture changes following retraction of the maxillary anterior bone segment after corticotomy. *Endod Dent Traumatol.* 1996;12 (1):38-43.
8. Wang Y, Zhang H, Sun W, Wang S, Zhang S, Zhu L et. al. Macrophages mediate corticotomy accelerated ortho-dontic tooth movement. *Sci Res.* 2018; 8 (1):1678-80.
9. Wu J, Xu L, Li C, Wang X, Jiang J. Exploration of key factors in Gingival Crevicular fluids from patients undergoing Periodontally Accelerated Osteogenic Orthodontics (PAOO) using proteome analysis. *BMC Oral Health.* 2023; 23 (1): 934-43.
10. Alikhani M, Raptis M, Zoldan B, Sangsuwon C, Lee YB, Alyami B, et al. Effect of micro-osteoperforations on the rate of tooth movement. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2013;144 (5): 639-48.
11. Raghav P, Khera AK, Preeti P, Jain S, Mohan S, Tiwari A. Effect of micro-osteoperforations on the rate of orthodontic tooth movement and expression of biomarkers: a randomized controlled

- clinical trial. *Dental Press J Orthod.* 2022; 27 (2):221-34.
12. Yildrum HS, Ates M, Gun IO, Kuru B, Cakirer B, Kuru LE. Osteocalcin and Cross-Linked C-Terminal Telopeptide of Type I Collagen in Gingival Crevicular Fluid during Piezocision Accelerated Orthodontic Tooth Movement: A Randomized Split-Mouth Study. *Niger J Clin Pract.* 2023 ; 26 (4): 470-7.
 13. Fernandes LS, Figueiredo DS, Oliveira DD, Houara RG, Rody WJ, Krishta canine retraction : a randomized controlled clinical trial. *Prog Orthod.* 2021 ; 22 (2):1-1.
 14. Stark TM, Sinclair PM. Effect of pulsed electromagnetic fields on orthodontic tooth movement. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 1987; 91(2): 91-104.
 15. Spadari GS, Zaniboni E, Vedovello SA, Santamaria MP, do Amaral ME, Dos Santos GM, Esquisatto MA, Mendonca FA, Santamaria-Jr M. Electrical stimulation enhances tissue reorganization during orthodontic tooth movement in rats. *Clin Oral Invest.* 2017; 21(1):111-20.
 16. Dutta S, Rout T, Patil AS, Deshmukh S. Use of electrical stimulation for accelerated orthodontics in humans: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Evid Based Dent.* 2024; 45 (1):1-9.
 17. Krishtab, S.I., Doroshenko, S.I. and Liutik, G.I. (1986) Use of vibratory action on the teeth to accelerate orthodontic treatment. *Stomatologiya (Mosk)* 1986; 65 (2): 61-63.
 18. Ohamae, M., Saito, S., Morohashi, T. et al. (2001) Biomechanical acceleration of experimental tooth movement by ultrasonic vibration in vivo part 1 : homo directional application of ultrasonication to orthodontic force. *Orthod Waves* 2001;60(2):201-212.
 19. Nishimura M, Chiba M, Ohashi T, Sato M, Shimizu Y, Igarashi K, et al. Periodontal tissue activation by vibration: intermittent stimulation by resonance vibration accelerates experimental tooth movement in rats. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2008; 133 (4): 572-83.
 20. Chatmahomngkol C, Pravitharangul A, Suttapreyasri S, Leethanakul C. The effect of compressive force combined with mechanical vibration on human alveolar bone osteoblasts. *J Oral Biol Craniofac Res.* 2019; 9 (1): 81-5.
 21. Kawasaki K, Shimizu N. Effects of low energy laser irradiation on bone remodeling during experimental tooth movement in rats. *Lasers in Surgery and Medicine: Laser Surg Med.* 2000; 26 (3): 282-91
 22. Limpanichkul W, Godfrey K, Srisuk N, Rattanayatikul C. Effects of low level laser therapy on the rate of orthodontic tooth movement. *OrthodCraniofac Res.* 2006;9(1):38-43.
 23. Fujita S, Yamaguchi M, Utsunomiya T, Yamamoto H, Kasai K. Low energy laser stimulates tooth movement velocity via expression of RANK and RANKL. *OrthodCraniofac. Res.*2008;11(3):143-55.
 24. Kim YD, Kim SS, Kim SJ, Kwon DW, Jeon ES, Son WS. Low-level laser irradiation facilitates fibronectin and collagen type I turnover during tooth movement in rats. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2010; 25 (2): 25-31.
 25. Yamaguchi M, Hayashi M, Fujita S, Yoshida T, Utsunomiya T, Yamamoto H, Kasai K. Low-energy laser irradiation facilitates the velocity of tooth movement and the expressions of matrix metalloproteinase-9, cathepsin K, and alpha (v) beta (3) integrin in rats. *Eur J Orthod.* 2010; 32 (2):131-9.
 26. Domínguez A, Gómez C, Palma JC. Effects of low level laser therapy on orthodontics: rate of tooth movement, pain, and release of RANKL and OPG in GCF. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2015; 30 (1): 915-23.
 27. Fernandes MR, Suzuki SS, Suzuki H, Martinez EF, Garcez AS. Photobiomodulation increases intrusion tooth movement and modulates IL6, IL8 and IL-1 β expression during orthodontically bone remodeling. *J Bio photonics.* 2019;12(10):201-22.
 28. Ekizer A, Uysal T, Güray E, Akkuş D. Effect of LED-mediated-photobiomodulation therapy on orthodontic tooth movement and root resorption in rats. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2015;30 (2):779-85.
 29. Kau CH, Kantarci A, Shaughnessy T, Vachiramon A, Santiwong P, de la Fuente A et. al. Photobiomodulation accelerates orthodontic alignment in the early phase of treatment. *Prog Orthod.* 2013;14 (1):1-9.
 30. Shankar S, Shetty SV, Nayak RS, Tewari N, Javed A. In vivo study of gingival crevicular fluid interleukin 1-beta (IL1- β) and prostaglandin-E2 (PGE-2) levels with pain perception after placement of elastomeric separators with and without low level laser therapy: An in vivo study. *IP Indian J Orthod Dentofacial Res.* 2023; 9 (4): 258-269.
 31. Saito S, Dr. Rosol TJ, Saito M, Ngan PW, Shanfeld J, Davidovitch Z. Bone resorbing activity and prostaglandin E produced by human periodontal ligament cells in vitro. *J Bone Miner Res.* 1990; 5 (10): 1013-8.
 32. Grieve III WG, Johnson GK, Moore RN, Reinhardt RA, DuBois LM. Prostaglandin E (PGE) and interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) levels in gingival crevicular fluid during human orthodontic tooth movement. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 1994;105 (4): 369-74.
 33. Lee W. Experimental study of the effect of prostaglandin administration on tooth movement with particular emphasis on the relationship to the method of PGE1 administration. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 1990; 98 (3): 231-41.
 34. Yamasaki K, Shibata Y, Imai S, Tani Y, Shibasaki Y, Fukuhara T. Clinical application of prostaglandin E1 (PGE1) upon orthodontic tooth movement. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 1984; 85 (6): 508-18.
 35. Kanzaki, H., Chiba, M., Arai, K. et al. Local RANKL gene transfer to the periodontal tissue accelerates orthodontic tooth movement. *Gene Ther.* 2006;13 (1): 678-85.